

Determination of recycled carbon fiber strength distribution using fiber bundle tensile test

Yoshiki SUGIMOTO¹, Yusuke IMAI¹ and Masaki HOJO²

¹Department of Multi-Material research Institute, Advanced Industrial Science and Technology (AIST)
4-205, Sakurazaka, Moriyama-ku, Nagoya, Aichi 463-8560, JAPAN
Email: y.sugimoto@aist.go.jp, web page: <https://www.aist.go.jp/>

²Kinki Polytechnic College
3-1-1, Kishinooka-cho, Kishiwada, Osaka 596-0817, JAPAN
Email: Hojo.Masaki@jeed.go.jp, web page: <https://www3.jeed.go.jp/osaka/college/index.html>

Keywords: Carbon fiber, Strength distribution, Recycle, Properties

ABSTRACT

In this study, we investigated the improvement in carbon fiber (CF) bundle tensile tests. To effectively evaluate the mechanical properties of CF using the fiber bundle tensile test, measurement system compliance correction considering nonlinear behavior and Weibull analysis using curve fitting were conducted. Weibull parameters were extracted by fitting the stress-strain curves, while considering the effect of the kinetic friction force. The obtained parameters from the fiber bundle tensile test correspond to those from the single fiber tensile test. This method was also applied to the recycled CF bundles. It was found that the recycled CF bundles have orientation distributions and tends to overestimate their strength. However, it was found that this method is suitable for screening of the recycle CF bundles.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibers (CFs) have high tensile strength and high tensile modulus reinforcement fibers and are used in various field, such as in aerospace and sports gears. The demand of CFs is increasing, and the reuse and recycling of CFs are necessary to meet the increasing demand [1, 2]. The main stream of matrix polymers for CF composites are mostly thermoset resins, such as epoxy resin, and the CFs are recovered from these composites by removing the matrix resin. Several methods are used to recover CFs from their matrix polymers; however, these methods tend to degrade the mechanical properties of the recycle CFs (rCFs) and their composites [3-5]. Therefore, it is very important to evaluate the mechanical properties of the rCF.

Single fiber tensile tests are commonly carried out to evaluate the mechanical properties of rCF [6]. The strength of CFs is usually follows Weibull distribution, and a large number of tests are needed to estimate the distribution. rCFs can have a wider strength distribution compared to the virgin CFs, owing to various damages suffered during their history of usage, and recovery processes. In addition, the damage stage of the rCFs during the recovery process is not uniform, even in the same batch rCFs. Therefore, a considerably greater number, typically hundreds, of tests is necessary to accurately evaluate the strength distribution of rCFs, which is time-consuming and laborious. Addition to this, recently continuous rCFs can be obtained from hydrogen pressure tanks and efficient evaluation methods for such continuous rCF are urgent.

To overcome these issues, the fiber bundle tensile test is considered an effective method to obtain the fiber strength distribution [7-13] with smaller numbers of tests. In this method, fiber bundle stress-strain curves are obtained experimentally, and the Weibull parameters, which express the fiber strength distribution, are derived from the stress-strain curves. To effectively evaluate the fiber strength distribution, precise strain measurements should be obtained. The strain can be obtained by using the measurement system compliance correction [7, 10] and an extensometer [8, 9, 10, 13]. Recently, digital image correlation analysis has been applied as a novel non-contact strain measurement method [12].

The advantages of the fiber bundle test methods are accepted, and they are applied to measure the strength distribution of various fibers, such as CFs [7, 8, 11, 13], silicon carbide fibers [12], and glass

fibers [9]. However, these methods are only applicable to fiber bundle specimens with well-defined bundle shapes, restricted fiber numbers, and lengths. In case of rCFs, it is difficult to prepare the required bundle specimen for the bundle test as the rCFs usually have a limited length of several tens of millimeters or less. Therefore, it is important to develop an improved test method that can effectively measure the strain of shorter and thinner bundles.

In this study, we investigated the effectiveness of the measurement system compliance correction method and the calculation method of Weibull parameters for the tensile test of CF bundles using specimens of different gauge lengths. The Weibull parameters were calculated considering the effect of kinetic friction between the fibers. In addition, the validity of the fiber bundle tensile test was examined by comparing the obtained Weibull parameters with those of the single fiber tensile tests. This test method was also applied to the rCF bundles and revealed the issues.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Virgin CF bundles with a width of 7 mm (T700S, Toray Ind.) and recycled CF bundles (Carbon Fiber recycle Industry co. Ltd.) were used in this study.

The CF bundles were not impregnated with polymers to effectively evaluate the fiber strength distribution. The bundle consisted of 12,000 fibers and was coated with a sizing agent for convergence. The sizing agent was not removed to avoid disruption of the fiber orientation.

The recycled CF bundles were obtained from aerospace parts by a pyrolysis method. The orientation of the recycled CF bundles was slightly disordered, so they were combed to align the fiber orientation. The thickness of the recycled CF bundles was below 0.15 mm. The cross-sectional area of the bundle was calculated by dividing the bundle liner density by the bundle density. The bundle liner density was obtained by measuring the bundle weight of the 300 mm length bundle, and a bundle density of 1.8 g/cm³ in the catalogue data was used for this calculation.

2.2 Fiber bundle tensile test

A schematic illustration for preparation of the fiber bundle tensile test specimen is shown in Fig. 1. Specimens that have both ends of the bundle tabbed are prepared as follows. First, a cardboard with a thickness of 0.5 mm was cut into pieces as tabs (20 mm × 60 mm) and spacers (5 mm × 6 mm). Then, the spacers were fixed on the tab, and an epoxy adhesive was painted on the tab. The CF bundle was placed on the adhesive with application of tension in order to keep the bundle straight, epoxy adhesive was painted over the bundle, and covered with another tab. In this study, the distance between the tabs was defined as the gauge length. In order to conduct the system elongation, virgin CF bundle tensile test specimens with gauge lengths of 10, 50, 75, and 100 mm were fabricated. Test specimens with gauge length of 50 mm were prepared for rCF.

Tensile tests of the fiber bundles were conducted using a universal testing machine (AG-Xplus 10 kN, Shimadzu Corp.) attached to a 5 kN load cell. A pneumatic flat grip attached to the universal joint was employed. The apparent strain rate, which is obtained by dividing the cross-head speed by the gauge length, was 1 %/min. The alignment of the test system is essential for achieving uniform loading to the bundle. Therefore, the alignment of the grips was adjusted by gripping the metal plate. The alignment of the specimen was carried out by suspending a string with a load to the lower tab and adjusting the string axis and tensile axis. To ensure the alignment of the specimens, the pretension of 5 N was applied to the specimens before the test.

Figure 1 Schematic illustration of the preparation of the specimen.

2.3 Single fiber tensile test

Single fiber tensile test specimens with a gauge length of 10 mm were prepared by fixing a single CF to the paper template. The specimen was placed on a tensile test machine (EZ-SX, Shimadzu Corp.) attached to a 10 N load cell. After scissoring both sides of the paper template, the tensile tests were conducted with a cross-head speed of 1 mm/min.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Load-displacement curves of fiber bundle tensile test

Load-displacement curves of the fiber bundle tensile tests with different gauge lengths specimens are presented in Fig. 2. Progressive failures were observed in specimens with gauge lengths above 50 mm. This may be due to the difference in compliance between the fiber bundle and the measurement system. While the compliance of the bundle is proportional to the fiber length and inversely proportional to the number of fibers in the bundle, that of the measurement system is almost constant. The compliance of the bundle decreases with a decrease in the gauge length. Therefore, if the fibers in the bundle broke partially, the compliance of the bundle remained at a small value. This indicates that the applied load remained almost constant, and resulted in an unstable brittle failure of the bundle. Further, it was observed that the peak load increased with a decrease in the gauge length, except for the specimen with a gauge length of 10 mm

Fig. 3 shows the pictures of the specimens before and after the fiber bundle tensile tests. The specimens with a gauge length longer than 50 mm were dense and straight before and during tensile tests, but expanded forms after the test, reflecting the undulation of fibers after fracture. In contrast, the fibers of the specimen with a gauge length of 10 mm showed almost limited winding after the tests and were substantially ruptured. These results correspond to the different load-displacement curves in Fig. 2.

Figure 2 Load -displacement curves of fiber bundle tensile tests with different gauge lengths.

Figure 3 Pictures of the fiber bundle specimens with a gauge length of (a) 1 cm and (b) 5 cm. The specimen on the left is before the test and the specimen on the right is after the test.

3.2 Correction of measurement system elongation

Total elongation, ΔL_{total} , is the sum of the fiber bundle elongation, ΔL_{fiber} , and the measurement system elongation, ΔL_{system} , and the following equation is established[16].

$$\Delta L_{total} = \Delta L_{fiber} + \Delta L_{system} = L_{fiber} \frac{P}{SE} + \alpha \cdot \Delta L_{system} \quad (1)$$

where P is tensile load, E is fiber tensile modulus, S is cross section area of the fiber bundle, L_{fiber} is gauge length and α is shape factor which is governed by the shape of the tab and the fiber bundle as follows:

$$\alpha = \frac{w_0(W - w_0) \cdot \ln\left(\frac{W}{w_1}\right)}{w_1(W - w_1) \cdot \ln\left(\frac{W}{w_0}\right)} \quad (2)$$

where W is adhesive width and w_1 is recycled CF bundle width and w_0 is virgin CF width which is used for measurement of system elongation. When $w_0 = w_1$, $\alpha = 1$.

Thus, the measurement system elongation at load P can be obtained from the slope of the plot of ΔL_{total} against the gauge length. Fig. 4(a) shows the relationship between ΔL_{total} and L_{fiber} at two loads of 250 N and 500 N. As shown in Fig. 4(a) the plots are on linear lines, and the system elongation can be obtained from the intercept of the lines.

Since the measured load was quite large in the current tests, the stress-strain relationship of the epoxy adhesive, which was used for fixing the tabs, was nonlinear. Hence, the measurement system elongation also exhibited nonlinear behavior. To evaluate the load dependence of the measurement system elongation, the measurement system elongation was calculated for various loads up to 1100 N with 50 N increments. The measurement system elongation of a fiber bundle with a width of 7 mm is represented in Fig. 4(b) with red symbols. From Fig. 4(b), it was confirmed that the measurement system elongation exhibited nonlinear behavior. By fitting the measurement system elongation with a quadratic function, $\Delta L_{\text{system}} = 2.31 \times 10^{-8}P^2 + 2.63 \times 10^{-4}P + 3.06 \times 10^{-2}$ was obtained as the equation of the measurement system elongation for the 7 mm width fiber bundle.

Figure 4 (a) Plots of total elongation, ΔL_{total} , versus gauge length, L_{fiber} , and (b) plots of measurement system elongation, ΔL_{system} versus load, P .

3.3 Stress-strain curves for virgin CF fiber bundle tensile test

The stress-strain curves for the 7 mm width virgin CF bundles are shown in Fig. 5. Here, the bundle fiber strain was calculated using gauge length and bundle elongation which was obtained by subtracting the elongation of the measurement system from the total elongation. The bundle stress was calculated by dividing the load by the initial bundle cross-sectional area. In all the specimens, except for the specimens with a gauge length of 10 mm, the initial slope in the small strain region was consistent, which indicated that system elongation correction was performed properly. The deviation of the specimens with gauge length of 10 mm considered to be due to the misalignment. Even if the shift between upper and lower tabs is the same, the tilt angle of the bundle from the loading direction becomes larger for shorter gauge length. Thus, higher test accuracy of equipment and specimen placement is required to effectively experiment with the short gauge length specimens.

Figure 5 Stress-strain curves of virgin CF bundles with different gauge lengths.

3.4 Weibull parameters obtained from fiber bundle tensile test

Assuming that the fiber bundle is pulled simultaneously without sagging and its strength follows Weibull distribution, its stress, σ_{measured} , can be expressed as follows [16].

$$\sigma_{\text{measured}} = E\varepsilon \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{L_{\text{fiber}}}{L_0} \left[\frac{E\varepsilon}{\sigma_0}\right]^m\right) + T \left\{1 - \exp\left(-\frac{L_{\text{fiber}}}{L_0} \left[\frac{E\varepsilon}{\sigma_0}\right]^m\right)\right\} \quad (3)$$

where m is Weibull shape parameter, σ_0 is Weibull scale parameter, ε is strain of the fiber bundle, E is tensile modulus of the bundle, T is friction force between fibers in the bundle, L_{fiber} is gauge length, and L_0 is reference length (1m). E , m , σ_0 , and T can be obtained by fitting stress-strain curves with equation (3).

The measured stress-strain curves for gauge lengths of 50 – 100 mm were fitted by equation (3) using generalized reduced gradient method [15] and fitting parameters were obtained. Fig. 6 shows the fitting results for the gauge length of 550 mm. It was confirmed that the whole region of the stress-strain curved was successfully fitted by the equation (3) considering the kinetic friction.

To evaluate the validity of the fiber bundle tests, the Weibull parameters obtained by the fiber bundle tests were compared to those obtained by the single fiber tensile tests. The Weibull parameters obtained by the CF bundle tensile tests corresponded moderately to those obtained by the single fiber tensile tests. Therefore, fiber bundle testing using compliance correction can be considered as a valid test method for evaluating the mechanical properties of fibers.

Figure 6 also shows the stress-strain curves from the tensile test of the rCF bundle. In this case, the rCFs originally had a tensile modulus of 230 GPa; however, the modulus of the fiber bundle was found to be low, at 51 GPa. This indicates that some fibers are not connected between the tabs. Although the rCF strength can change, the rCF tensile modulus is typically maintained. Thus, we assumed that the tensile modulus of the rCFs remained unchanged, and we obtained the rCF Weibull parameters by fitting a modified theoretical equation that included a parameter indicating the initial rCF break fraction. As a result, the Weibull parameters of the fiber were obtained: a scale parameter of 2.7 GPa and a shape parameter of 6.8. This value is in accordance with the tensile strength of virgin fiber bundles, indicating that the recycling process properly maintains fiber strength. However, this result also indicates that fibers may break during specimen fabrication (or the recycling process), so special care may be needed to obtain reliable results.

Figure 6 Stress-strain curves of virgin CF and recycled CF bundles.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, fiber bundle tensile tests were conducted to evaluate the tensile strength of CF and rCF bundle. The dependence of the measurement system elongation on the fiber width was investigated. By using equation considering the effect of kinetic friction in the theoretical bundle stress-strain relationship, the Weibull parameters and kinetic friction were evaluated. The obtained Weibull parameters obtained from the fiber bundle tensile test roughly corresponded with those obtained from the single fiber tensile tests, and the validity of the fiber bundle tensile tests was confirmed. For the specimens with a short gauge length, the test was difficult due to the misalignment of the specimen from loading axis.

Even though rCF bundle seem perfectly continuous fibers, they contained discontinuous fibers. Even in such case the strength distribution could be evaluated supposing the tensile modulus. Although this method has some point such as preparation of the specimens that need to be overcome, this method can be considered as an effective method to evaluate the tensile strength of recycled CFs.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This paper is based on results obtained from a project commissioned by the New Energy and Industrial Technology Development Organization (NEDO).

REFERENCES

- [1] Zhang J, Chevali VS, Wang H and Wang CH. Current status of carbon fibre and carbon fibre composites recycling. *Composites, Part B* **193**(2020)
- [2] Verma S, Balasubramaniam B, and Gupta RK. Recycling, reclamation and re-manufacturing of carbon fibres. *Curr. Opin. Green Sustainable Chem.* **13**(2018)86-90.
- [3] Sun H, Guo G, M SA, Xu W, Zhang Q, Zhu JH, Xing F. Recycling of carbon fibers from carbon fiber reinforced polymer using electrochemical method. *Composite, Part A* **78**(2015):10-17.
- [4] Ma C, Sanchez-Rodriguez D Kamo T. Influence of thermal treatment on the properties of carbon fiber reinforced plastics under various conditions. *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* **178**(2020):109199.
- [5] Cai GB, Wada M, Ohsawa I, Kitaoka S, and Takahashi J. Tensile properties of recycled carbon fibers subjected to superheated steam treatment under various conditions. *Composite, Part B* **133**(2020), 105869.
- [6] ISO 11566:1996 Carbon fibre - Determination of the tensile properties of single-filament specimens-.
- [7] Chi Z, Cho TW, and Determination of single fibre strength distribution from bundle testings. *J. Mater. Sci.* **19**(1984)3319-3324.
- [8] Calard V and Lamon J, Failure of fiber bundles, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* **64** (2004) 701-710.
- [9] R'Mili M, Moevus M, and Godin N. Statistical fracture of E-glass fibres using a bundle tensile test and acoustic emission monitoring. *Compos. Sci. Technol.* **68**(2008)1800-1808.
- [10] ISO 22459:2020 Fine ceramics (advanced ceramics, advanced technical ceramics) — Reinforcement of ceramic composites — Determination of distribution of tensile strength and tensile strain to failure of filaments within a multifilament tow at ambient temperature
- [11] Zhou Y, Wang Y, Zia Y, and Jeelani S. Tensile behavior of carbon fiber bundles at different strain rate, *Mater. Lett.* **64**(2010) 246-248.

- [12] Callaway EB and Zok FW. Strength of ceramic fiber bundles: Theory and practice. *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* **100**(2017)5306-5317.
- [13] Boulanghien M, R'Mili M, Bernhart G, Berthet F, and Soudais Y. Mechanical Characterization of Carbon fibres Recycled by steam Thermolysis: A statical Approach. *Adv. Mater. Sci. Eng.* (2018)8630232.
- [14] Naito K, Tanaka Y, Yang JM, and Kagawa Y. Tensile Properties of ultrahigh strength PAN-based, ultrahigh modulus pitch-based and high ductility pitch-based carbon fibers, *Carbon***46**(2008)189-195.
- [15] Lasdon LS, Waren AD, Jain A, and Ratner M. Design and testing of a generalized reduced gradient code for nonlinear programming. *ACM T Math. Softw.*, **4** (1) (1978), pp. 34-50
- [16] Sugimoto Y, Imai Y, Hojo M *et al.* Determination of Carbon Fiber Strength Distribution Using Bundle Fiber Tensile Test: Correction of Measurement System Elongation and Kinetic Friction Between Fibers in the Fiber Bundle. *J. Mater. Res.* **36**, 961–969 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1557/s43578-020-00043-y>